

Characterization and Susceptibility Patterns of Pathogens Causing Otorrhoea

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Abstract

Background: Approximately 65-300 million cases of chronic otitis media occur worldwide. Mainstay of chronic discharging ears is meticulous aural toilet and empirical antimicrobials given systemically or as topical preparation. Majority of practitioners do not routinely send specimens of the discharge for microbiological analysis unless the discharge is refractory to treatment. However, Empiric treatment of ear infection is not always appropriate as the pathogen and their drug susceptibility patterns can change over time and it could contribute to the development of antimicrobial resistance in the long run.

Objectives: This study was performed to characterize the pathogens isolated in cases of ear discharge and to study the antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of the obtained bacterial isolates.

Methods: This retrospective study was conducted in the department of microbiology, Government T.D Medical College, Alappuzha.

Results: Bacterial isolates were the predominant cause of ear infection in all age groups. The commonest bacterial pathogen obtained was pseudomonas spp (29.6%) followed by staphylococcus aureus (13.9%). Aspergillus spp was the commonest isolated fungi (13.9%) followed by Candida spp (8.1%). Flouroquinolones were sensitive only in 35% of gram-negative isolates and aminoglycosides were sensitive only in 46.3% of gram-negative isolates. Methicillin resistance was noted only in 4.2 % of the isolates.

Conclusion: Empirical therapy in ear infection cases must be used with caution. The most effective antibiotics for gram negative isolates was found to be piperacillin-tazobactam and cefipime. The most effective antibiotic for Staphylococcus aureus isolates was found to be cloxacillin, cefazolin and co-trimoxazole.

Keywords: Otorrhoea, Pseudomonas spp, Aspergillus spp, Ciprofloxacin, Aminoglycosides.

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Introduction

Otorrhoea refers to any discharge that comes out from the external auditory canal including blood, pus, or mucous fluid.[1] It typically develops as a side effect of ear infections such as cholesteatoma-causing chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM), acute otitis externa, and acute otitis media.[2]

Approximately 65-300 million cases of CSOM occur worldwide. Prevalence is related to poor socio-economic conditions. [3,4,5] As per WHO reports, otitis media is the predominant cause of hearing damage in 42 million people worldwide.[6] Globally, 28000 deaths are attributed per year to complications arising secondary to chronic suppurative otitis media.[3]

The mainstay of chronic discharging ears is a meticulous aural toilet and empirical antimicrobials given systemically or as a topical preparation.[7] The majority of clinicians don't send samples of ear discharge for microbiological analysis until the

empirical antibiotics have failed.[8] Topical quinolones have been the most commonly used drugs for empirical treatment of ear infections for the past 40 years with minimal adverse effects. Trials have also shown quinolones to be active even in ear discharge with tympanostomy tubes. [9,10] However, empirical treatment for ear infections is not recommended because the pathogen and its drug susceptibility patterns are dynamic and may eventually lead to the emergence of antibiotic resistance.[11]

Aim of the Study

1. To characterize the pathogens isolated in cases of ear discharge
2. To study the antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of the obtained bacterial isolates.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology, Government T.D

Medical College, Alappuzha. All ear swabs received from various clinical departments from 1st January 2018- 1st January 2019 were included in the study.

Data Collection

All the data necessary was obtained from the clinical isolate register maintained in the Department of Microbiology.

Sample Processing

Ear swabs were processed in the bacteriology unit of the Department of Microbiology in the Central lab of the Medical College. Three types of agar were inoculated with the ear swab samples: blood, Mac Conkey, and chocolate. Following a 24-48-hour incubation period, the isolates' cultural traits were noted. For the purpose of identifying the bacterial isolates, Gram staining, biochemical tests such as the nitrate, lactose, sucrose, and mannitol tests, triple sugar iron agar, urease, indole, and citrate tests, and fermentation on sugar medium were carried out. To identify the fungal isolates, methods such as gram staining, germ tube testing,

and lactophenol cotton blue staining were used. Further subcultures were performed on Sabarauds dextrose agar if necessary for identification and incubated at room temperature.

Mueller Hinton agar plates were subjected to antibiotic susceptibility tests employing the Kirby Bauer method. The antibiotic discs used were Penicillin, Ampicillin, ceftriaxone, cefotaxime, cefazolin, amikacin, ceftazidime, co-trimoxazole, erythromycin, clindamycin, piperacillin-tazobactam, Cefaperazone-sulbactam, meropenem according to the identified isolates. The antibiotic zone sizes were interpreted based on CLSI 2019 guidelines. Antifungal susceptibility testing could not be done due to financial constraints.

Results

Of the 345 samples received, monomicrobial isolates were obtained in 248 ear swabs, a polymicrobial growth was obtained in 55 ear swabs, and in 42 ear swabs no pathogen or skin contaminants were obtained in culture. Gram-negative bacilli predominated in the monomicrobial growth (34.5%).

Table 1: Percentage of isolates obtained

	Frequency	Percentage
Gram-positive organisms	51	14.8%
Gram-negative organisms	119	34.5%
Fungal isolates	78	22.6%
No pathogen isolated	36	10.4%
Mixed bacterial growth	55	15.9%
Contaminants grown	6	1.7%
Total	345	

153 samples were from male patients and 192 samples were from female patients.

Figure 1: Gender distribution of study sample

The commonest pathogen causing ear infections in both sexes were bacterial isolates, 78% (78/100) in

males and 62% (92/148) in females, p-value of 0.008.

Table 2: Pathogens obtained in both gender

	Male	Female	Total
Bacterial pathogen	78	92	170
Fungal pathogen	22	56	78
Total	100	148	248

The study's subjects ranged in age from 1 to 75 years old, with a mean age of 36. Patients in the age range of 0 to 30 provided 139 samples, patients in the age range of 31 to 60 provided 149 samples, and patients in the age range of 61 to 75 provided

57 samples. In all of the three classes, bacterial isolates predominated as 48.2%(67/139) in the age group 0-30, 50.3%(75/149) in the age group 30-60, and 49.1%(28/57)in the age group 61-75, p-value 0.048.

Table 3: Pathogens isolated in various age groups

	0-30	31-60	61 and above	Total
Bacterial pathogen	67	75	28	170
Fungal pathogen	25	43	10	78
Mixed bacterial growth	23	17	15	55
No pathogen+contaminants grown	24	14	4	42
Total	139	149	57	345

Of the 248 pure isolates, 170 were bacterial pathogens and 78 were fungal pathogens. The commonest bacterial pathogen obtained was *Pseudomonas* spp (102, 29.6%) followed by *Staphylococcus aureus*

(48, 13.9%). *Aspergillus* spp was the commonest isolated fungi (48,13.9%) followed by *Candida* spp (28, 8.1%)

Figure 2: Frequency of individual isolates obtained in the study

Table 4: Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of the obtained isolates

Antibiotic	sensitive	resistant	total
Pseudomonas spp			
Amikacin	39(38.2%)	63(61.8%)	102
Ciprofloxacin	37(36.3%)	65(63.7%)	102
Ceftazidime	49(48%)	53(52%)	102
Meropenem	49(48%)	53(52%)	102
Piperacillin-tazobactam	73(71.5%)	29(28.5%)	102
Cefipime	62(60.8%)	40(39.2%)	102
Staphylococcus aureus			
Penicillin	5(10.4%)	43(89.6%)	48
Cefoxitin	46(95.8%)	2(4.2%)	48
Clindamycin	29(60.4%)	19(39.6%)	48
Cotrimoxazole	40(83.3%)	8(16.7%)	48

Erythromycin	11(22.9%)	37(77.1%)	48
Cefazolin	45(93.7%)	3(6.3%)	48
Enterobacteriaceae			
Amikacin	13(100%)	0.00%	13
Ciprofloxacin	8(61.5%)	5(38.5%)	13
Cefotaxime	7(53.8%)	6(46.2%)	13
Cotrimoxazole	11(84.6%)	2(15.4%)	13
Piperacillin-tazobactam	13(100%)	0.00%	13
Meropenem	13(100%)	0.00%	13
Cefaperazone sulbactam	13(100%)	0.00%	13
Cefipime	13(100%)	0.00%	13
Streptococcus spp			
Penicillin	13(100%)	0.00%	13
Ampicillin	13(100%)	0.00%	13
Erythromycin	2(66.7%)	1(33.3%)	13
Cefazolin	13(100%)	0.00%	13
Acinetobacter spp			
Amikacin	3(75%)	1(25%)	4
Ciprofloxacin	2(50%)	2(50%)	4
Cefotaxime	2(50%)	2(50%)	4
Piperacillin-tazobactam	3(75%)	1(25%)	4
Meropenem	3(75%)	1(25%)	4
Cefaperazone-sulbactam	4(100%)	0.00%	4
Cefipime	3(75%)	1(25%)	4

Figure 3: Antibiotic resistance pattern of common antibiotics used for gram negative isolates

Of the gram-negative bacilli isolates, 25.2% were resistant to piperacillin-tazobactam, 53.7% to amikacin, and 65% to ciprofloxacin.

Discussion

Pseudomonas spp. was the most common isolate found in this investigation, followed by *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Pseudomonas* species are usually associated with chronic otitis media and otitis externa. It is a typical warm-humid environmental saprophyte that has been seen to invade the external auditory canal. [12,13] Similar findings were observed by Gul et al, Mansoor et al.[14,15]

Fungi are common causes of CSOM, especially in hot and humid regions. The majority of cases involve *Candida* spp. and *Aspergillus* spp. The com-

monest fungal isolate obtained in this study was also *Aspergillus* spp followed by *Candida* spp. This is comparable to the findings of Vishwanath et al, Ibekwe et al. [16,17]

The resistance pattern of the most common isolate, *Pseudomonas* spp ranged from 28.5% - 63.7%. The highest resistance rate was noted for the most widely used drug ciprofloxacin as 65 out of 102 (63.7%) isolates were resistant. This is at variance with the observations of Madana et al [18]

The most sensitive antibiotics against *Pseudomonas* spp were piperacillin-tazobactam (71.5%) and cefipime (60.8%). Only 38.2% of isolates were sensitive to aminoglycosides and only 48% of isolates were sensitive to ceftazidime.

Of the 48 *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates, methicillin resistance was noted in 2 isolates. The most effective antibiotic against *Staphylococcus* was cloxacillin (95.8%), cefazolin (93.7%), and cotrimoxazole (83.3%). Maximum resistance was noted against Penicillin (89.6%) followed by Erythromycin (77.1%). This type of high resistance to penicillin as well as an increase in methicillin resistance was also pointed out by Park et al. [19]

Of the isolates of Enterobacteriaceae, 38.5% exhibited resistance to ciprofloxacin. Cefipime, piperacillin-tazobactam, and amikacin were all effective against all of the isolates. 84.6% of the isolates were sensitive to co-trimoxazole.

75% of the *Acinetobacter* spp isolated were sensitive to amikacin, cefipime, piperacillin-tazobactam. Only 50% of isolates were sensitive to ciprofloxacin.

The sensitivity pattern could not be compared to previous isolates from this institution as no similar studies were conducted here in the past.

Conclusion

The predominant pathogens of ear infection in this study were gram-negative bacilli (34.5%) followed by fungal pathogens (22.6%) and gram-positive organisms (14.8%). *Staphylococcus aureus* is the second most frequent bacterial agent linked to ear infections in this institute, after *Pseudomonas* spp. Of the isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*, 4.2% had methicillin resistance. *Aspergillus* spp. were the most often isolated fungal species, followed by *Candida* spp. Ciprofloxacin was sensitive only in 35% of gram-negative isolates. It should be used with caution as empirical therapy in ear infection cases. Gentamicin cannot be tested due to the unavailability of the antibiotic discs. The most effective antibiotics for gram-negative isolates were found to be piperacillin-tazobactam and cefipime. The most effective antibiotic for *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates was found to be cloxacillin, cefazolin, and co-trimoxazole.

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